

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Diagne**FIRST NAME:** Mohamed Amadou Dial**PROGRAM CODE:** MDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. GULMA**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Using gathering thoughts, what does freewriting means?

- Jot down things that you already know about your subject, and the questions you have about it.
- Write freely for at least 5-10 minutes, exploring your subject from a number of different angles.¹**
- Create a cluster with your specific subject as the nucleus word.
- Think carefully about a subject by answering the following types of questions.

2. The key of a clear written report revising them?

- Put long introductory phrases and clauses.
- Make long subjects.

¹ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 54.

Put key actions in nouns.

Put key actions in verbs.²

3. **What is the order for the basic steps in writing an essay?**

Analyze the question and define key terms, Establish a possible thesis/ point of view.

Research the topic. Use credible academic sources for support and evidence.

Take notes from your readings. Write an essay plan and organize your ideas.

There is no strict order.³

4. **What three parts should include the structure of the essay?**

Introduction – Analysis – Conclusion.

Introduction – Evidence – Conclusion.

Introduction – Body – Conclusion.⁴

Introduction – Analysis – Evidence.

5. **The stage Prewriting during the process of writing consists in?**

Choosing and gathering.⁵

Checking for style and accuracy.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 75-76.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

⁴ Ibid., 3.

⁵ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 9.

- Writing the first Draft.
 - Improving your writing.
6. **What is the correct order when citing with Turabian several common types of sources in notes bibliographies (B)?**
- Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication.
 - Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book.
 - Author's First Name, Author's Last Name. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication.
 - Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name, Date of Publication.**⁶
7. **When I must provide a citation?**
- When you express your ideas, theories, arguments, conclusions.
 - Whenever you use another person's ideas in their own words.**⁷
 - When you develop your research method.
 - Where surveys and experiments are designed and carried out by you.
8. **Why we have to provide citations and references?**
- You have gathered evidence to support your ideas and arguments.**⁸

⁶ Kate L. Turabian, 91.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 55-57.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 55.

- You haven't used credible, good quality sources.
- You have not read widely and at an appropriate academic level.
- You allow your tutor not to differentiate between your own work and the work of others and to locate the sources you have used.

9. **Which of the following sentences is not true regarding colons?**

- Colons are most often used to indicate that an expansion, qualification or explanation is about to follow.
- Use colons at the end of headings.⁹**
- Colons do not require the next word to start with a capital.
- Colons should be closed up to the preceding word, unlike in French usage.

10. **When writing, what is the correct chronological time order?**

- First, second, then, next, later, etc.¹⁰**
- First, second, then, later, next etc.
- First, then, second, next, later, etc.
- First, second, later, then, next etc.

⁹ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. Seventh edition: August 2011.

¹⁰ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, 60.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.